

CHARGE AND STABILITY OF COLLOIDS, PART X.
STUDIES ON THE RELEASE OF COUNTER IONS FROM
Cr (OH)₃ SOL ON THE ADDITION OF PAIRS
OF ELECTROLYTES

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The effect of the addition of pairs of electrolytes on release of counter ions from Cr (OH)₃ sol. has been studied. It has been found that in almost all cases the amount of released chlorine is greater than the calculated value. This means that the mixture induces more instability a necessary consequence of which is that there should be no ionic antagonism.

In the previous communication of this series (p. 357) the effect of adding pairs of electrolytes to Fe(OH)₃ sol, has been studied. In this paper it has been endeavoured to show the effect of the same pairs of electrolytes with Cr (OH)₃ sol under similar conditions in order to find out if this sol also behaves similar to the ferric hydroxide sol.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The sol of chromium hydroxide was prepared by the method given in a previous paper of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 219). The method of procedure was the same as in the previous communication with Fe (OH)₃ sol.

TABLE I
Chlorine displaced from Cr(OH)₃ sol on adding *N*/10-KIO₃.

KIO ₃ added to sol.	π	$\alpha\text{Cl} \times 10^3$	Total [Cl] $\times 10^3$	[Cl] displ. $\times 10^3$	[Cl] eqvt. to [IO ₃] $\times 10^3$
0.00 c.c.	0.0527 volts	10.20	11.25	0.00	0.00
0.50	0.0502	11.25	12.41	1.16	5.00
1.00	0.0488	11.87	13.12	1.87	10.00
2.00	0.0476	12.44	13.76	2.51	20.00
3.00	0.0465	12.98	14.37	3.12	30.00
4.00	0.0441	14.26	15.86	4.61	40.00
5.00	0.0413	15.90	17.72	6.47	50.00

TABLE II
Chlorine displaced from Cr (OH)₃ sol on adding *N*/50-K₂SO₄.

K ₂ SO ₄ added to sol.	π	$\alpha\text{Cl} \times 10^3$	Total [Cl] $\times 10^3$	[Cl] displ. $\times 10^3$	[Cl] eqvt. to [SO ₄] added $\times 10^3$
0.00 c.c.	0.0527 volts	10.20	11.25	0.00	0.00
0.50	0.0506	11.07	12.20	0.95	1.00
1.00	0.0487	11.92	13.16	1.91	2.00
1.50	0.0451	13.71	15.22	3.97	3.00
2.00	0.0434	14.65	16.30	5.05	4.00
2.50	0.0424	15.23	16.97	5.72	5.00
3.00	0.0414	15.83	17.67	6.42	6.00

TABLE III

Chlorine displaced from $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ sol on adding $N/100$ -K-citrate to it.

K-cit. added to sol.	π	$\alpha\text{Cl} \times 10^3$	Total $[\text{Cl}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{Cl}]$ displ. $\times 10^3$	$[\text{Cl}]$ eqvt. to $[\text{Cit}]$ added $\times 10^3$
0.00 c.c.	0.0527 volts	10.20	11.25	0.00	0.00
0.50	0.0502	11.20	12.36	1.11	0.50
1.00	0.0488	11.87	13.11	1.88	1.00
2.00	0.0469	12.78	14.15	2.60	2.00
3.00	0.0542	13.66	15.14	3.89	3.00
4.00	0.0436	14.53	16.15	4.90	4.00
5.00	0.0428	15.29	17.03	5.78	5.00

TABLE IV

Chlorine displaced from $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ sol on adding $N/50$ - $\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4 + N/10$ - KIO_3 .

0.5 c.c. $\text{K}_2\text{SO}_4 +$ c.c. of KIO_3 .	π	$\alpha\text{Cl} \times 10^3$	Total $[\text{Cl}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{Cl}]$ displ. $\times 10^3$	$[\text{Cl}]$ eqvt. to $[\text{SO}_4]$ & $[\text{IO}_3] \times 10^3$
0.00	0.0527 volts	10.20	11.25	0.00	0.00
0.50	0.0492	11.88	12.90	1.65	7.00
1.00	0.0468	12.84	14.21	2.96	12.00
1.50	0.0443	14.15	15.75	4.50	17.00
2.00	0.0425	15.17	16.92	5.67	22.50
2.50	0.0414	15.83	17.69	6.44	27.00
3.00	0.0405	16.40	18.85	7.10	32.00

TABLE V

Chlorine displaced from $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ sol on adding $N/100$ -K-citr. + $N/10$ - KIO_3 .

1 c.c. K-citr. + c.c. of KIO_3	π	$\alpha\text{Cl} \times 10^3$	Total $[\text{Cl}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{Cl}]$ displ. $\times 10^3$	$[\text{Cl}]$ eqvt. to $[\text{Cit}]$ & $[\text{IO}_3]$ added. $\times 10^3$
0.00	0.0527 volts	10.20	11.25	0.00	0.00
1.00	0.0496	11.51	12.70	1.45	11.00
1.50	0.0480	12.25	13.53	2.28	16.00
2.00	0.0472	12.64	13.97	3.72	21.00
2.50	0.0457	13.89	14.85	3.60	26.00
3.00	0.0440	14.31	15.91	4.66	31.00
3.50	0.0427	15.05	16.76	5.51	36.00

TABLE VI

Chlorine displaced from $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ sol on adding $N/10\text{-KIO}_3 + N/50\text{-K}_2\text{SO}_4$.

1 c.c. of $\text{KIO}_3 +$ c.c. K_2SO_4	π	$\alpha\text{Cl} \times 10^3$	Total [Cl] $\times 10^3$	[Cl] displ. $\times 10^3$	[Cl] eqvt. to $[\text{IO}_3]$ & $[\text{SO}_4] \times 10^3$
0.00	0.0527 volts	10.20	11.25	0.00	0.00
0.25	0.0485	12.01	13.27	2.03	10.50
0.50	0.0449	13.82	15.35	4.10	11.00
1.00	0.0425	15.17	16.91	5.66	12.00
1.50	0.0399	16.79	18.78	7.53	13.00
2.00	0.0373	18.67	20.84	9.59	14.00
3.00	0.0335	21.55	24.41	13.16	16.00

TABLE VII

Chlorine displaced from $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ sol on adding $N/100\text{-K-citrate} + N/50\text{-K}_2\text{SO}_4$.

1 c.c. K-cit+c.c. K_2SO_4	π	$\alpha\text{Cl} \times 10^3$	Total [Cl] $\times 10^3$	[Cl] displ. $\times 10^3$	[Cl] eqvt. to [Cit] & $[\text{SO}_4] \times 10^3$
0.00	0.0527 volts	10.20	11.25	0.00	0.00
0.50	0.0475	12.49	13.80	2.55	2.00
1.00	0.0455	13.49	14.97	3.32	3.00
1.50	0.0440	14.31	15.91	4.66	4.00
2.00	0.0433	14.70	16.36	5.11	5.00
2.50	0.0423	15.29	17.05	5.80	6.00
3.00	0.0413	15.90	17.74	6.49	7.00

TABLE VIII

Chlorine displaced from $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ on adding $N/10\text{-KIO}_3 + N/100\text{-K-citrate}$.

1 c.c. $\text{KIO}_3 +$ c.c. of K-cit.	π	$\alpha\text{Cl} \times 10^3$	Total [Cl] $\times 10^3$	[Cl] displ. $\times 10^3$	[Cl] eqvt. to $[\text{IO}_3]$ & $[\text{Cit}] \times 10^3$
0.00	0.0527 volts	10.20	11.25	0.00	0.00
0.50	0.0478	12.34	13.65	2.40	10.50
1.00	0.0442	14.20	15.78	4.53	11.00
2.00	0.0415	14.59	16.23	4.98	12.0
2.50	0.0424	15.23	16.95	5.70	12.50
3.00	0.0409	16.15	18.08	6.77	13.00
4.00	0.0398	16.85	18.55	7.60	14.00

TABLE IX

Chlorine displaced from $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ sol on adding $N/50\text{-K}_2\text{SO}_4 + N/100\text{-K-citrate}$.

I c.c. of K_2SO_4 +c.c. K-cit.	π	$\alpha\text{Cl} \times 10^3$	Total [Cl] $\times 10^3$	[Cl] displ. $\times 10^3$	[Cl] eqvt. to $[\text{SO}_4]$ & [Cit]. $\times 10^3$
0.00	0.0627 volts	10.20	11.25	0.00	0.00
0.50	0.0464	13.03	14.48	3.23	2.60
1.00	0.0448	13.87	15.45	4.20	3.00
1.50	0.0481	14.82	16.52	5.27	3.60
2.00	0.0418	15.59	17.40	6.15	4.00
3.00	0.0402	16.60	18.54	7.29	5.00
4.00	0.0389	17.46	19.53	8.28	6.00

DISCUSSION

From the above results the following tables have been calculated.

Concentration of $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ sol, as $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3 = 8.88$ g. per litre.

Chlorine content of the sol = 0.054 g. per litre.

Purity of the sol *i.e.*, $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Cl} = 127$.

TABLE X

Displacement of chlorine ions from chromium hydroxide sol.

Electro- lyte added	Displace- ment of [Cl] from the sol		Electro- lyte added	Displace- ment of [Cl] from the sol		Electro- lyte added	Displace- ment of [Cl] from the sol	
	[Chlorine] equiv. of the electrolyte added	[Chlorine] equiv. of the electrolyte added		[Chlorine] equiv. of the electrolyte added	[Chlorine] equiv. of the electrolyte added			
	$N/10\text{-KIO}_3$			$N/50\text{-K}_2\text{SO}_4$			$N/100\text{-K-citrate}$	
0.50 c.c.	1.16	5.00	0.50 c.c.	0.95	1.00	0.50 c.c.	1.11	0.50
1.00	1.87	10.00	1.00	1.91	2.00	1.00	1.86	1.00
2.00	2.51	20.00	1.50	3.87	3.00	2.00	2.60	2.00
3.00	3.12	30.00	2.00	5.05	4.00	3.00	3.89	3.00
4.00	4.81	40.00	2.25	5.78	4.50	4.00	4.90	4.00
5.00	6.47	50.00	3.00	6.42	6.00	5.00	5.78	5.00

From the above table it will be seen that with chromium hydroxide sol the displacement of chlorine ions is almost the same with all the electrolytes. This can be explained on the basis of the purity of the sol. It has been observed previously that with these sols there is always a certain purity below which chlorine ions released is always

less than the equivalent of the added electrolyte, whereas with less pure sols the released chlorine is greater than the added electrolyte. The ferric hydroxide sol in previous paper is purer than this limit, but here the $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ sol is less pure.

In the case of $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ sol it is observed that the quantity of chlorine ions released at the coagulation concentration is approximately the same. This peculiar behaviour is connected with the impure nature of $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ sol.

From the results recorded in Tables I—IX, the following tables have been calculated in which the release of the chlorine ions as observed and calculated when adding one electrolyte in presence of another is given. The theoretical release due to the combined effect of both the electrolytes has also been calculated and given in columns 2 and 5 of the following tables

TABLE XI

Displacement of Cl ions from $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ sol when $N/50\text{-K}_2\text{SO}_4 + N/10\text{-KIO}_3$ and $N/100\text{-K-citrate} + N/10\text{-KIO}_3$ are added to it in pairs.

0.5 c.c. K_2SO_4 + c.c. of KIO_3	Calc.	Obs.	1 c.c. K-citr. + c.c. of KIO_3	Calc.	Obs.	[Cl] eqvt. to electro- lyte added $\times 10^3$
0.50	2.11	1.65	...	...	...	6.00
1.00	2.82	2.98	1.00	3.73	1.45	11.00
1.50	3.15	4.50	1.50	4.08	2.28	16.00
2.00	3.48	5.67	2.00	4.37	2.72	21.00
2.50	3.78	6.44	2.50	4.68	3.60	26.00
3.00	4.07	7.10	3.00	4.98	4.66	31.00
3.50	...	...	3.50	5.26	5.51	36.00

TABLE XII

Displacement of Cl ions from $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ sol when $N/10\text{-KIO}_3 + N/50\text{-K}_2\text{SO}_4$ and $N/10\text{-KIO}_3 + N/100\text{-K-citrate}$ are added to it in pairs.

1 c.c. KIO_3 + c.c. of K_2SO_4	Calc.	Obs.	1 c.c. KIO_3 + c.c. K-cit.	Calc.	Obs.	[Cl] eqvt. to electro- lyte added $\times 10^3$
0.25	2.37	2.02	0.50	2.98	2.40	10.50
0.50	2.82	4.10	1.00	3.73	4.53	11.00
1.00	3.78	5.65	2.00	4.47	4.98	12.00
...	...	...	2.50	5.00	5.70	12.50
1.50	5.84	7.53	3.00	5.70	6.77	13.00
2.00	6.92	9.59	4.00	6.77	7.60	14.00
3.00	8.29	13.16	...	...	...	16.00

TABLE XIII

Displacement of Cl ions from $\text{Cr}(\text{OH})_3$ sol when $N/100$ -K-citrate + $N/50$ - K_2SO_4 and $N/50$ - K_2SO_4 + $N/100$ -K-citrate are added to it in pairs.

1 c.c. K-citr. + c.c. K_2SO_4	Theor.	Obs.	1 c.c. K_2SO_4 + c.c. of K-cit.	Theor.	Obs.	[Cl] eqvt. to elec- trolyte added $\times 10^3$
0.50	2.81	2.55	...	...	...	2.60
...	...	...	0.50	2.08	3.23	2.50
1.00	3.77	3.32	1.00	2.82	4.20	3.00
...	...	...	1.50	3.23	5.27	3.50
1.50	5.83	4.86	2.00	3.55	6.15	4.00
...	...	...	3.00	4.81	7.29	5.00
...	...	...	4.00	5.85	8.28	6.00

From the above results it is found that with chromium hydroxide sol as well, the amount of released chlorine is greater than the calculated value. This means that the mixture induces more instability than the combined effects of the two electrolytes when taken in singles. A necessary consequence of this is that there should be no positive ionic antagonism i.e., the amount of electrolyte necessary to coagulate, should be less than the additive. This has been observed by previous workers with these sols, but with other pairs of electrolytes.

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